

Locus of Control and Anxiety among the Students from Medical and Non-Medical College

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Abstract:

Aim of the present study the difference between medical and non-medical students on locus of control and anxiety. To assess the locus of control, Locus of control (LOC) of Vohra (1992) and to assess the anxiety, Anxiety scale of Cattell, Krug and Scheier used and were administered 60 student from medical and non-medical college of Pune City of Maharashtra. Finding indicate that internal and external locus of control significantly not differed among students from non-medical college and students from medical college. In case of anxiety, significant difference found between students from non-medical college and students from medical college. Students from medical college found higher level of anxiety than students from non-medical college.

Keywords: Locus of control, anxiety, Students from Medical college and non-medical college.

Introduction:

In education, focal point of control often refers to how students perceive the cause of their academic success or failure. Students with "internal locus of control" often believe that their success or failure is the result of the effort and hard work they have put in during their studies. Excessive stress in medical education makes it difficult for students to resolve interpersonal conflicts caused by prior stress. A significant proportion of medical students develop an anxiety disorder due to the long-term effects of stress on emotional and behavioral symptoms.

Internal Locus of Control:

According to Rotter (1966), Locus of Control states that individual's perception about the underlying main causes of events in his/her life. Or, more simply: Do you believe that your destiny is controlled by yourself or by external forces (such as fate, god, or powerful others).

For example, students with an internal locus of control, score may blame poor grades for poor performance, while students with external locus of control, scores may blame teachers or an unfair test for poor performance.

A person with an external locus of control who believes that academic success or failure is due to luck or chance, higher power, or the influence of others, rather than their own actions. They also struggle more with procrastination and difficult tasks.

Anxiety:

Kaplan and Sadock (1996) "Anxiety is characterized by pervasive, unpleasant, and vague feelings of fear, often accompanied by autonomic symptoms such as headache, sweating, palpitations, chest tightness, and mild stomach discomfort"

American Psychological Association, (APA) (2009) "Anxiety is an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, anxious thoughts, and physical changes such as increased blood pressure, intrusive thoughts or anxiety. They may avoid certain situations because of anxiety.

Rationale and Significance of the Study:

The present study try to find out difference between students from medical college and non-medical college on locus of control and anxiety.

Students with "internal locus of control" often believe that their success or failure is the result of the effort and hard work they have put in during their studies. Excessive stress in medical education makes it difficult for students to resolve interpersonal conflicts caused by prior stress. Result of the study will be useful for academic institution, medical sector, counsellor, parents and students.

Review of Literature:

Rinn and Boazman (2014) surveyed college students with high potential. Their research concerns "scores of control, academic self-concept, and academic dishonesty". He used statistical techniques. He found the effect of control on academic dishonesty. He concluded that the lay group

had no significant predictors of academic dishonesty. They also found multiple relationships among variables for the composite group, the honored group, and even the unhonored group.

Prochazka (2014) studied the relationship between L-O-C (control score) and procrastination in learning. He randomly interviewed 145 students studying a bachelor's degree in humanities. 100 students completed a questionnaire provided by the scholarship holder. The results showed that “correlation analysis did not show a statistically significant relationship between the research variables ($r = -0.15$, $p = 0.15$)”. According to this theory, the theory that there may be a relationship between internal/external locus of control and learning delay remains unconfirmed

Aggrawal (2006) has researched on the topic of the role of emotional intelligence in relationships in the context of school deprivation and anxiety. He found that for girls who were more emotionally intelligent, academic deprivation and anxiety were positive while girls with low emotional intelligence were not. Emotionally intelligent girls have low anxiety levels during study and results-oriented exams.

Pahwa, et al (2008) investigated the topic of pre-exam anxiety among medical students and how it relates to personality. He found that as exams approached, anxiety levels increased, especially in a study of students with neurosis and extroverted temperaments. Anxiety levels are also linked to certain personality traits.

Vijayakumari (2010) investigated the secondary context of the relationship between anxiety at school and academic achievement. She found that school anxiety had a negative effect on academic achievement, but it was completely different for boys and girls.

Statement of the problem:

“To study the locus of control and anxiety among the medical and non-medical college students.”

Objectives:

1. To study the difference between students from medical and non-medical college on locus of control.
2. To study the difference between students from medical and non-medical college on anxiety.

Hypotheses:

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1. There would be significance difference between students from medical and non-medical college on internal and external locus of control.
2. There would be significance difference between students from medical and non-medical college on anxiety.

Research Design:

It is between group design in which researcher try to find out difference between students from medical and non-medical college on locus of control and anxiety.

Variables:

Independent Variable: Students from medical and non-medical college

Dependent Variable: Emotional Competence

Operational Definition:

- 1) Internal Locus of control: Score obtained on internal locus of control factors of locus of control and measured by Locus of control (LOC) Vohra (1992).
- 2) External Locus of Control: Score obtained on external locus of control factors of locus of control and measured by Locus of control (LOC) Vohra (1992).
- 3) Anxiety: Score obtained on all factors anxiety and measured by Anxiety scale by Cattell, Krug and Scheier (1959).

Sample and Data Collection Procedure:

In the present study, total 30 student selected from medical college and 30 students selected from non-medical college of Pune district of Maharashtra by using purposive sampling. Age range was 20 to 30 years of the sample. Set of questionnaire including personal data sheet were administered to these sample.

Tools of the Study:

Following standardized scales having all the psychological properties will be used.

1. Locus of control (LOC) Vohra (1992).

This 24 likert type rating scale measures locus of control in three dimensions, i.e. powerful on others (P) chance control (C) and individual control (I). The test reliability is .76 and validity is .54.

2. Anxiety scale by Cattell, Krug and Scheier (1959).

This scale is standardized and having psychological properties. This 40 items questionnaire provides a convenient and practical measure of anxiety level. It is constituted on the basis of 5 principle 16 P.F factors namely emotional instability suspiciousness, guilt proneness low integration and tension. The test reliability is .89 and validity is .94.

Result:

Internal locus of control and external locus of control significantly not differed among the students from medical and non-medical college ($t=1.15$, $p>0.05$). External locus of control significantly not differed among the students from medical and non-medical college First hypothesis stating that “There would be significance difference between students from medical and non-medical college on internal and external locus of control.” is rejected.

Anxiety significantly differed among students from medical and non-medical college ($t=7.87$, $p<0.01$). Mean for students from medical college is=44.43, $SD=4.45$ and mean for student from non-medical college students is 35.26, $SD=4.57$ on anxiety. It shown that students from medical college significantly higher level of anxiety than student from non-medical college. Second hypothesis stating that “There would be significance difference between students from medical and non-medical college on anxiety” is accepted.

Conclusion:

1. Internal and external locus of control significantly not differed among students from non-medical college and students from medical college.
2. Students from medical college found higher level of anxiety than students from non-medical college.

Limitations:

1. Present cannot be generalized on students from non-professional college.

2. Sample size in the present study only 60.

Suggestions:

1. Students from non-professional college can be considered in the in the future study.
2. Large sample size can be consider.

Implications:

Students from professional college need to develop emotional competency. It is required to develop emotional competency. Then students can better perform in their academic achievement.

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